

CEPI | Brighton Collaboration

Database with mapping of relevant pathogens, vaccines and stakeholders for each special population group focused on CEPI's portfolio.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The maternal immunization group developed a list of pathogens of interest for maternal immunization based on 1) the priority pathogens list from CEPI 2) review of the literature and 3) input from experts from the Maternal Immunization Work Group (MIWG).

Based on the list of AESI for Lassa fever developed by WP2, we also provided a list of AESI for pregnancy studies in general and additional AESI of relevance to studies of Lassa fever vaccines in pregnancy. A prioritization of AESI for Lassa fever studies and the rationale for the prioritization was provided.

The final list of pathogens of interest and the AESI document were presented to SPEAC-CEPI in March 2023. The prioritized AESI list for Lassa Fever and rationale for prioritization was presented to SPEAC-CEPI in September 2023. The lists of pathogens and AESI are intended for use to incorporate the pathogens of interest for maternal immunization and respective vaccines in development into a database being developed in conjunction with the SPEAC Digitization group and to evaluate vaccine safety in pregnancy along with SPEAC Active Vaccine Safety Surveillance work package.

1. Introduction

Timely inclusion of special populations in vaccination strategies during outbreaks, epidemics and pandemics, is a key SPEAC-CEPI objective. SPEAC WP5 – Special Populations – seeks to support and facilitate CEPI efforts to ensure that groups that require specific considerations for vaccine development and implementation can benefit from timely participation in research and vaccine roll out. These groups include pregnant persons, pediatric populations (newborns, infants, children and adolescents), and high-risk groups which include those who are older, immunocompromised, or have complex or multiple comorbidities that increase their risk for disease.

2. Objectives

1. To develop a list of pathogens of special interest to maternal immunization and the associated vaccines in development, to incorporate into a database/system of priority pathogens for vaccine evaluation in pregnancy and early childhood.
2. To maintain a living document updating the list of pathogens of interest and their respective vaccines in development for maternal immunization as CEPI priorities and maternal immunization research evolves.
3. To contribute to and actively participate in the incorporation of the list of pathogens of interest and vaccines in development into a database developed by SPEAC Digital Transformation.
4. To assess the safety of vaccines in pregnancy in collaboration with the SPEAC Active Vaccine Safety Surveillance Work Package (WP6) by developing a list of AE, SAE and AESI relevant to maternal immunization.

3. Methods

An expert working group (WG) of experts in maternal and pediatric immunization (Annex 3) reviewed existing literature and proposed a list of pathogens of interest to maternal vaccination strategies based on the burden of disease to the mother, the fetus, and/or the newborn.

The WG also reviewed and commented on the CEPI provided priority list (Table 1). The WG utilized data shared from a literature review regarding disease burden and status of vaccine development, as well as their expertise to comment and propose pathogens for inclusion.

The list of pathogens of interest that was generated by SPEAC therefore includes both CEPI priority pathogens as well as other pathogens of relevance for maternal immunization (Table 2). The MIWG reviewed the list and provided comments over a period of time (2-4 weeks) leading to a virtual meeting where compiled comments and suggestions were discussed. A final list of pathogens of interest to maternal immunization activities was agreed upon and classified by the type of disease they cause and the target populations for intervention (Table 2).

In addition, SPEAC and the expert WG developed a list of AESI relevant to maternal immunization studies/studies in pregnant women and provided specific guidance on AESI for Lassa fever vaccine studies. (Table 3) These were incorporated to a document generated by the SPEAC Active Safety Surveillance team WP6, adding to the guidance provided by WP2 (Annex 1). AESI for non-pregnant populations applicable to Lassa fever and recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus (VSV)-based platform and available tools and resources can be found in SPEAC WP2 deliverable D2.5.1 Lassa fever landscape analysis and AESI list update (author: Barbara Law). A prioritization of AESI for Lassa fever vaccine studies in pregnancy and the rationale for the prioritization was provided. (Table 4)

Finally, we developed a spreadsheet with the outputs of this effort to track the progress of clinical development and data generated in pre-clinical and clinical studies for Lassa fever vaccines. (Annex 2) This spreadsheet will remain a living document with near real-time updates as data becomes available. Data for other pathogens (other than for Lassa fever) will continue to be added. Regarding Lassa Fever Vaccines, the initial focus has been on the vaccines under development by IAVI and by Emergent BioSolutions, given that other vaccines (Themis, Oxford) do not seem have data supporting continuation of evaluation in human clinical trials¹. The data will be used to incorporate into a database by the SPEAC Digital Transformation team (WP4).

4. Results

4.1 The expert WG reviewed and endorsed the CEPI priority pathogens list as described in Table 1.

Priority disease/ Pathogen	Special population target	Need for timely inclusion in vaccine development	Need for vaccine safety /AESI surveillance	Existing tools
Lassa Fever	Pregnant women, children and adolescents, and medically at-risk groups	Yes - due to fatality risk. Yes - HCW exposure	Yes	GAIA/BC Definitions AESI
Chikungunya	Pregnant women and newborns	Yes - risk for mother and congenital infection	Yes	GAIA/BC Definitions AESI
<i>Nipah-Virus</i>	Medically at-risk groups	Yes - HCW exposure	Yes	BC Definitions AESI
Coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 variant	Pregnant women Medically at-risk children and adults	Yes - due to direct risk in all special populations	Yes	GAIA/BC Definitions AESI
<i>Pandemic Influenza</i>	Pregnant women Medically at-risk children and adults	Yes - due to direct risk in all special populations	Yes	GAIA/BC Definitions AESI
Disease X	Potentially all groups, including children, at risk adults and pregnant women	Yes - due to direct risk in all special populations or HCW exposure	Yes	GAIA/BC Definitions AESI

Table 1. CEPI PRIORITY PATHOGENS WITH IMPACT ON SPECIAL POPULATIONS (List provided by CEPI, reviewed but not modified by MIWG)
 Abbreviations: AESI: adverse events of special interest; BC: Brighton Collaboration; GAIA: Global Alignment of Immunization safety Assessment in pregnancy; HCW: healthcare worker.

4.2 The expert MIWG developed a list of pathogens of interest to maternal immunization as described in Table 2.

Problem	Pathogens	Options
Pneumonia and Respiratory Infections	Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) Influenza seasonal/pandemic SARS-CoV-2/coronaviruses Pertussis	Maternal vaccine, passive antibody, infant vaccine Maternal vaccine and infant Maternal vaccine and infant Maternal and infant vaccine
Neonatal Sepsis	Group B Streptococcus Tetanus Gram Negatives (e.g., E. coli, Klebsiella) Listeria	Maternal vaccination Maternal Vaccination Pre-Pregnancy and option for maternal vaccination
Congenital Anomalies	Cytomegalovirus (CMV)	Pre-pregnancy and option for maternal vaccination
Maternal-Fetal-Infant Infection	Malaria Ebola Lassa Fever (CEPI Priority pathogen) Hepatitis E	Pre-pregnancy and option for maternal vaccination Pediatric vaccination
Other	Nipah Virus Chikungunya (CEPI priority pathogen) Zika Dengue Cholera Yellow Fever	Pre-pregnancy and option for maternal vaccination Some could be option for pediatric vaccination

Table 2. Pathogens of Interest to Maternal Immunization (developed by WP5 expert MIWG). The highlighted pathogens are those considered highly relevant for maternal immunization within each problem category.

4.3 AESI of relevance to maternal immunization studies and to Lassa fever vaccine studies.

4.3.1 AESI list applicable to maternal immunization studies as suggested by the Special Populations and the MIWG

AESI relevant for maternal immunization studies include outcomes (mother, fetus, infant), which are relevant and should be included in any vaccine evaluated in pregnancy. These are also relevant to Lassa vaccine studies in addition to those proposed by SPEAC for non-pregnant populations (WP2).

- Maternal death
- Neonatal death
- Spontaneous abortion/miscarriage
- Stillbirth
- Preterm delivery (maternal outcome) and preterm birth (infant outcome)
- Maternal hemorrhage (antenatal/peripartum/postnatal)
- Low birth weight (LBW)
- Small for gestational age (SGA)
- Intra Uterine Growth Restriction (IUGR)
- Congenital anomalies, including microcephaly
- Thrombosis (mother)
- Consider myocarditis/pericarditis - depending on platform.
- Consider neonatal sepsis

4.3.2 Suggested additions of the MIWG to the AESI list for maternal immunization applicable to Lassa Fever and recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus (VSV)-based vaccine platform

- Maternal Lassa infection
- Maternal Lassa severe disease
- Vertical Lassa infection to newborn
- Newborn or infant severe Lassa disease
- Maternal death from Lassa
- Fetal death from Lassa
- Neonatal death from Lassa
- Abnormal bleeding in mother
- Anemia in mother
- Hepatitis/jaundice (mother)
- Acute kidney injury (AKI) (mother)
- Puerperal sepsis (can use endometritis/septic abortion Case Definition)
- Sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) (mother and infant)

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- Encephalitis (mostly mother)
- Consider: Swollen baby syndrome (infant, reported in Lassa)

4.3.3 Prioritization of AESIs for maternal immunization applicable to Lassa fever (presented to CEPI during Clinical Office Week meeting, September 2023)

SAE / AE of Relevance	AESI and rationale for special consideration
Death: Maternal death, Fetal loss (SAB and Stillbirth), Neonatal death, Infant death	Preterm birth (signal in pregnancy studies)
Congenital anomalies	Sensorineural hearing loss in mother and infant (associated with Lassa fever)
Fetal/Infant events with potential for health consequences: IUGR, LBW, SGA, Neonatal sepsis	Lassa infection and severe disease in mother, fetus, or infant (vaccine associated viremia, vertical infection)
Maternal events with potential for health consequences: Encephalitis, Myocarditis, Pericarditis, Hypertension, Eclampsia, Preeclampsia, Anemia, AKI, Hepatitis, ARDS, Chorioamnionitis, Endometritis, Sepsis	Death from Lassa fever in mother, fetus, or infant (vaccine enhanced disease)
	Maternal hemorrhage or thrombotic events (antenatal/peripartum/postnatal) (relevant to Lassa fever, vaccine platform)

Table 3. Prioritization of AESIs for maternal immunization applicable to Lassa fever

5. References

1. Sulis G, Peebles A, Basta NE. Lassa fever vaccine candidates: A scoping review of vaccine clinical trials. *Trop Med Int Health*. 2023 Jun;28(6):420-431. doi: 10.1111/tmi.13876. Epub 2023 Apr 24. PMID: 37095630; PMCID: PMC10247453.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1

Lassa Fever Safety Notes

Lassa Fever Background for Active Safety Surveillance Development – Notes from WP6. Author: Andy Stergachis

Topic	Characteristic	Comment
Causative agent	Lassa virus (LASV), belonging to the Arenaviridae family.	
Incubation period	1-3 weeks	www.cdc.gov/vhf/lassa/symptoms/index.html
Geography	Known to be endemic in: Benin, Ghana, Guinea, Liberia, Mali, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, and Togo.	https://cepi.net/research_dev/priority-diseases/
Burden	Estimated 100,000 – 300,000 cases annually, resulting in approximately 5,000 deaths annually.	Challenges with clinical diagnosis as well as limited existing surveillance infrastructure means that the disease is likely significantly under-reported and that incidence rates in countries with known endemic disease are imprecise
Clinical presentation	80% of Lassa fever cases have no symptoms. Symptomatic cases range widely in terms of severity: from mild headache or fever to more serious symptoms such as vomiting, swelling of the face, pain in the chest, back and abdomen, and bleeding from body parts, including the eyes and nose.	Approximately 1 in 5 cases will experience severe symptoms.
Sequelae	~1% of cases are fatal, usually within two weeks of onset of symptoms. However, the case-fatality ratio is much higher in severe cases, with 15-20% of severe hospitalized cases being fatal. Hearing loss, which occurs in 25% of recovered patients.	https://cepi.net/research_dev/priority-diseases/
Special populations	There is also increased risk among women in the late stages of pregnancy, with maternal death and/or fetal loss occurring in 80% of cases during the third trimester.	The Lassa fever virus has a higher affinity for the vascular tissues of the fetus and placenta
Vaccines	No vaccines are currently approved for human use	
Vaccine development in CEPI portfolio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International AIDS Vaccine Initiative (IAVI)* Emergent BioSolutions* University of Oxford Inovio Pharmaceuticals 	https://cepi.net/research_dev/priority-diseases/ Updated 13 February 2023

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<p>Potential sources of information for background rates & potential sentinel sites</p>	<p>*Entered Phase I clinical trials.</p> <p>CEPI is funding the Enable Lassa Research Programme A multi-country epidemiology study in which partners are gathering data on Lassa fever to prepare for future Lassa vaccine clinical trials in West Africa. Up to 23,000 participants will be enrolled into studies in outbreak-prone areas—Benin, Guinea, Liberia, Nigeria and Sierra Leone—with the first participants enrolled in Nigeria December 2020.</p>	<p>Launched with Nigeria Lassa Fever Research consortium consisting of the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) and supporting partners. “Funding will be used to train staff to carry out the studies and provide equipment to support the program’s operation. As such, Enable is likely to not just benefit Lassa fever research, but also build laboratory capacity to complement the work on other emerging infectious diseases which may impact the region, including COVID-19.” Rates of potential infection will be measured in participants through standardized observational measures – ‘active surveillance’ with repeat health status assessments by a field worker through home visits or phone meetings to assess the health status of participants, and ‘passive surveillance’ where participants will be encouraged to report potential illness or to self-present at a health facility and the suspected or confirmed case is then recorded.</p>
	<p>Enable Sites: NIGERIA Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC), Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital (ISTH), Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Owo, Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital Abakaliki (AEFUTHA), Redeemer’s University Nigeria (RUN) and the African Field Epidemiology Network (AFENET). Together, the Nigerian partners make up the NiLE project of the Enable. BENIN Fondation pour la Recherche Scientifique (FO RS) LIBERIA Co-led by University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (UNC) and Phebe Hospital in partnership with the National Public Health Institute of Liberia (NPHIL) SIERRA LEONE Co-led by Kenema Government Hospital (KGH) and Tulane University</p>	<p>Implementing Partners: P95 will act as program coordinator, providing scientific and operational oversight to all coordinating partners and country study implementation teams as well as program-level project management. The Margan Clinical Research Organization (MMARCRO), based in Accra, Ghana, supports P95 through in-country field implementation and study monitoring support. Epicentre, a Paris-based organization conducting field epidemiology activities, research projects and training sessions in support of Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF); leads development of the programme data management system; is providing training and support to staff operating at Enable study sites; and</p>

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	<p>GUINEA Université Gamal Nasser de Conakry (UGANC) in partnership with Robert Koch Institute (RKI)</p>	<p>supervising the data collection, management, and analysis processes. The Bernard Nocht Institute for Tropical Medicine, based in Hamburg, Germany, will support the Enable program through laboratory expertise and support to country implementing partners, including staff training, laboratory process development, and quality assurance.</p>
<p>Treatment</p>	<p>Ribavirin has been used with success in Lassa fever patients. It has been shown to be most effective when given early in the course of the illness. Patients should also receive supportive care consisting of maintenance of appropriate fluid and electrolyte balance, oxygenation and blood pressure, as well as treatment of any other complicating infection. The safety of Ribavirin in pregnancy has not been established.</p>	<p>www.cdc.gov/vhf/lassa/symptoms/index.html</p>

Annex 2

Vaccines Tracking Spreadsheet – Lassa Fever

GENERL INFORMATION	AVAILABLE DATA	AVAILABLE REFERENCES	COMMENTS	KEY STAKEHOLDERS	EXISTING TOOLS	WP REQUESTS AND OUTPUTS
<p>IAVI</p> <p>Vaccine name construct: rVSVΔG-LASV-GPC. Recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus vector (rVSV) based. rVSVΔG-LASV-GPC is a viral vector-based vaccine candidate jointly developed by the International AIDS Vaccine Initiative (IAVI) and the Public Health Agency of Canada (PHAC). This vaccine utilises a recombinant form of the Vesicular Stomatitis Virus (rVSV) (i.e., the same platform used for the rVSV-vectored Ebola Zaire vaccine, ERVEBO®) to express the LASV glycoprotein (Josiah</p>	<p>Provided high level protection from LF in animal studies.</p> <p>Phase I studies: IAVI is the primary sponsor of the ‘Lassa Vaccine Efficacy and Prevention for West Africa’ (LEAP4WA) project, which includes a series of clinical trials of rVSVΔG-LASV-GPC. The phase 1 trial (NCT04794218 and PACTR2021 06625781067) started enrolment in June 2021, with estimated completion of follow-up in January 2024, and comprises two steps: dose escalation (conducted across three sites in the United States) and dose group expansion (carried out in one site in Liberia). This triple-blind (participant, care provider, investigator) trial makes use of permuted block</p>	<p>A review of Lassa vaccine candidates. Curr Opin Virol. 2019 Aug;37:105-111. doi: 10.1016/j.coviro.2019.07.006. Lassa fever vaccine candidates: A scoping review of vaccine clinical trials. Sulis G, Peebles A, Basta NE. Trop Med Int Health. 2023 Jun;28(6):420-431. doi: 10.1111/tmi.13876. Epub 2023 Apr 24. PMID:37095630</p> <p>Vaccine Candidates against Arenavirus Infections. Saito T, Reyna RA, Taniguchi S, Littlefield K, Paessler S, Maruyama J. Vaccines (Basel). 2023 Mar 13;11(3):635. doi: 10.3390/vaccines11030635. PMID: 36992218</p> <p>A recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus-based Lassa fever vaccine protects guinea pigs and macaques against challenge with geographically</p>	<p>Most likely to enter phase III first. Might include pediatric populations and pregnant women. Uses same platform (rVSV) used for the rVSV-vectored Ebola Zaire vaccine ERVEBO (licensed by Merck and registered in 8 African countries). Effective immunization with rVSV-LASV/GPC requires a</p>	<p>CEPI/IAVI/SPEAC/BC</p>	<p>GAIA/BC Definitions, AESI list</p>	<p>Request: Input on Safety endpoints and considerations regarding Inclusion of pregnant women in trials (12/2/2022). Input regarding inclusion in phase 2 or 3 clinical trials vs. pregnancy studies (May 2023). Unexpected pregnancies protocol (proposed Feb 2023-in development)</p> <p>Output: Need for DART studies? Key questions pregnancy module. Lassa fever vaccines review manuscript. Assessment of strategies for</p>

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<p>strain), requires intramuscular administration and does not need to be frozen. VSV, which rarely infects humans and—when it does—generally produces an asymptomatic infection, has several advantages as a vaccine vector, such as the ability to potentially harbor large transgenes and the inability to integrate into the host genome.</p> <p>Phase of development: Phase I-II</p> <p>Current vs. Special population target Special population target: Pregnant women, children and adolescents,</p>	<p>randomization to assign participants to one of seven experimental groups or placebo, with all participants receiving a single dose on Day 1 with a follow-up of 12 months. All primary outcomes are safety-related, whereas secondary outcomes include the evaluation of the antibody response as well as various measures of vaccine shedding and viral RNA levels in bodily fluids. Most eligibility criteria align with those of the other LF vaccine phase 1 trials. The phase 2 trial (PACTR202210840719552) is set to start recruiting a total of 612 individuals in August 2023 across three sites located in Liberia, Nigeria, and Ghana. In this triple-blind trial, simple randomization will be used to assign participants to receive the vaccine or placebo, and each of them</p>	<p>and genetically distinct Lassa viruses.</p> <p>Safronetz D, Mire C, Rosenke K, Feldmann F, Haddock E, Geisbert T, Feldmann H. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2015 Apr 17;9(4):e0003736. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0003736. eCollection 2015 Apr. PMID: 25884628</p> <p>A Lassa Fever Live-Attenuated Vaccine Based on Codon Deoptimization of the Viral Glycoprotein Gene.</p> <p>Cai Y, Ye C, Cheng B, Nogales A, Iwasaki M, Yu S, Cooper K, Liu DX, Hart R, Adams R, Brady T, Postnikova EN, Kurtz J, St Claire M, Kuhn JH, de la Torre JC, Martínez-Sobrido L. mBio. 2020 Feb 25;11(1):e00039-20. doi: 10.1128/mBio.00039-20. PMID: 32098811</p>	<p>high dose that might cause significant VSIV-associated side effects.</p>			<p>evaluation in pregnancy within phase2-3 clinical trials in non-pregnant populations vs. within focused pregnancy study (May 2023 presentation to CEPI).</p> <p>Unexpected pregnancies protocol (in development)</p> <p>Living systematic review proposal – safe in pregnancy group</p>
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<p>and medically at-risk groups</p> <p>Current target: Non pregnant adults, adolescents, children (age de-escalation)"</p>	<p>will be followed-up for 6 months. The study population will include a wider range of individuals compared to phase 1 trials: most notably, the age range will be 18 months to 70 years, and a subset of participants will be people living with HIV who are receiving antiretroviral treatment and have a good enough viro-immunological profile (viral load <50 copies/ml). This trial is aimed at further examining the vaccine candidate's safety profile (primary outcome) and evaluating humoral immune responses (secondary outcomes) in a broader and more heterogeneous population relative to earlier phase trials."</p>					
<p>Emergent BioSolutions</p>	<p>Phase 1 randomized, placebo-controlled, dose-escalation study, will</p>			<p>The VesiculoVax™ vaccine delivery platform is the</p>		<p>Request: Input on Safety endpoints and</p>

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<p>Vaccine name construct: LASV - rVSV vectored vaccine</p> <p>Phase of development: Phase I-II</p> <p>Current vs. Special population target Special population target: Pregnant women, children and adolescents, and medically at-risk groups</p> <p>Current target: Non-pregnant healthy adults, adolescents, children (de-escalation)</p>	<p>evaluate the safety and immunogenicity of Emergent’s rVSV-vectored Lassa virus vaccine in approximately 36 healthy adults at the Navrongo Health Research Centre and Kintampo Health Research Centre in Ghana.</p> <p>Phase 1 Study: Emergent Biosolutions’ trial of EBS-LASV (PACTR2021 08781239363), began recruitment in August 2022 at two sites in Ghana, with estimated completion of follow-up in September 2023. This double-blind (care provider, participant) trial has a target sample size of 108 adult participants, to be assigned to one of 10 experimental groups or placebo through simple randomization. Depending on the trial arm, each participant will receive either two doses (on Days 1 and 29) or four doses (on</p>			<p>result of basic research funding provided by the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, National Institutes of Health (NIH), and National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) initially to Yale University and subsequently to Profectus (Auro Vaccines)</p>		<p>considerations regarding Inclusion of pregnant women in trials (12/2/2022). Input regarding inclusion in phase 2 or 3 clinical trials vs. pregnancy studies (May 2023). Unexpected pregnancies protocol (proposed Feb 2023- in development)</p> <p>Output: Need for DART studies? Key questions pregnancy module. Lassa fever vaccines review manuscript. Assessment of strategies for evaluation in pregnancy within phase2-3 clinical trials in non-pregnant populations vs. within focused</p>
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	<p>Days 1, 15, 29 and 57) of the active product or placebo. This trial is mainly focused on dose escalation and dose selection, with safety and vaccine viral shedding as primary outcomes, and humoral response indicators as secondary outcomes. Participants' eligibility criteria align with those of most other Lassa vaccine trials; notably, 'prior residence, any time in the past, greater than 30 days in a LASV-endemic region (as per latest available WHO data)' constitutes an exclusion criterion for this trial even though the country of recruitment is Ghana.</p>				<p>pregnancy study (May 2023 presentation to CEPI).</p> <p>Unexpected pregnancies protocol (in development)</p> <p>Living systematic review proposal – safe in pregnancy group</p>
<p>OXFORD</p> <p>Vaccine name construct: ChAdOX1 vectored LF</p>	<p>Guinea pig study. No documented evidence supports the protective efficacy of either chimpanzee adenovirus-</p>		<p>Guinea pig study. No documented evidence supports the</p>		<p>Request: Input on Safety endpoints and considerations regarding Inclusion</p>

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<p>vaccine encoding the Josiah strain LASV glycogen precursor (GPC) gene</p> <p>Phase of development: Phase I</p> <p>Current vs. Special population target Special population target: Pregnant women, children and adolescents, and medically at-risk groups</p> <p>Current target: Non pregnant adults</p>	<p>based or mRNA-based LASV vaccine candidates in LF animal models.</p>		<p>protective efficacy of either chimpanzee adenovirus-based or mRNA-based LASV vaccine candidates in LF animal models</p>		<p>of pregnant women in trials (12/2/2022)</p> <p>Output: Same as above as needed if development proceeds.</p>
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Annex 3

Maternal Immunization Working Group membership

Full name	Title or position	Affiliation	Conflict	If conflict is YES
Ruth A Karron	Professor	Department of International Health, Bloomberg school of Public Health	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Angela Gentile	Head of the Epidemiology Department	Hospital de Niños R. Gutierrez, University of Buenos Aires	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Esperanca Julia Pires Sevene Comiche	Associate Professor of Clinical Pharmacology	Eduardo Mondlane University	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Terri Brrok Hyde	Medical Epidemiologist	CDC	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Clare Louise Cutland	Scientific coordinator, Wits-Alive	Wits African Leadership in Vaccinology Expertise, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Magdalena Babinska	Consultant	World Health Organization	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Proma Paul	Assistant Professor	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	

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Chrissie Jones	Dr / Associate Professor in Paediatric Infectious Diseases	University of Southampton, UK	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Sascha Ellington	Epidemiologist and Lead, Influenza Prevention and Control Team	National Center for Immunization and Respiratory Diseases, U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Samantha M Olson	Epidemiologist	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Anna Catherine Seale	Senior Program Officer	Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, LSHTM, Warwick University	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Geeta Krishna Swamy	Haywood Brown Distinguished Professor of Women's Health	Duke University	CONFLICT OF INTEREST	Chair for Independent Data Monitoring Committee for Pfizer Group b Strep vaccine trials and GSK RSV vaccine trials, author contributor to UpToDate on listeria in pregnancy, safety event adjudication for Moderna RSV vaccine trials in pregnancy, GSK expert contributor on congenital CMV, Medscape educational contributor on congenital CMV, Sanofi Vaccines in Pregnancy education contributor
Mercedes Bonet	Dr	WHO	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Dana Meaney-Delman	Branch Chief Infant Outcomes Monitoring Research	CDC	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	

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	and Prevention Branch			
Lee Fairlie				
Darcie Everett	Medical Officer	U.S. FDA	CONFLICT OF INTEREST	Potential for conflict with non-financial interests as a result of my employment at the U.S. FDA.
Beate Kampmann	Professor of Global Health	Charite Universitatsmedizin, Berlin, Germany	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Tara Jatlaoui	Medical Officer	CDC	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Proma Paul	Assistant Professor	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Christine Jones	Associate Professor in Paediatric Infectious Diseases	University of Southampton	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Terri Hyde	Vaccine Introduction Team Lead	CDC	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	
Andy Stergachis	Vaccine Safety	University of Washington, Seattle	NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST	